

D1.6 Standardisation landscape and applicable standards

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Executive Summary

Steel4Fatigue project aims to investigate fatigue-optimised solutions for dynamic components in the automotive industry. It will achieve this by introducing new materials and technologies to reduce the weight of trucks and cars by 10%. These solutions will be based on specially developed materials with high fatigue performance (AHSS and spring steels), advanced computer modelling for accurate fatigue prediction, and innovative experimental methodologies to reduce testing time. The project will also focus on minimising environmental impact evaluated through life cycle assessment, reducing energy consumption and material usage through improved steelmaking processes, and enhancing fatigue performance to facilitate wider market adoption of Steel4Fatigue solutions. Attention will be given to steelmaking, including internal defects and scrap quality, as well as manufacturing processes like cold forming and mechanical shearing, to better understand their impact on the fatigue performance of cyclic-loaded components. To achieve these goals, the project will develop methods for evaluating these effects and improving the fatigue design of selected demonstrators. It will also explore microstructures for optimal fatigue performance. Two industrial demonstrators will be defined to validate the proposed solutions. The project's contributions include reducing lead times to market through advanced fatigue testing methodologies and models. The outcomes will provide materials, modelling, and experimental tools for designing fatigue-resistant parts across multiple sectors. Practical guidelines will be established for factors such as proposed microstructures, advanced testing, modelling approaches, and the influence of manufacturing and steelmaking processes on part performance.

The Spanish Association for Standardization - UNE, as National Standardization Body (NSB) and member of CEN-CENELEC, is a partner in the Steel4Fatigue project whose goal is to provide support regarding the standardization tasks included in the deliverable D6 "D1.6 Standardization landscape and applicable standards".

This deliverable has been prepared to guide the published standards and under-development standards that can be relevant, helpful, and applicable to Steel4Fatigue. The aim is to provide starting information to ensure compatibility and interoperability with established technologies, expressed through standards. This is done in collaboration with all partners.

Moreover, it serves as the basis to establish the strategy for the following activity, "Contribution to standardization." This may involve contact and interaction with relevant Technical Committees (TCs), potential contribution to the development of new or under-review standards, and/or modification proposals for existing standards. In addition, it can help in the future to identify standardization gaps that can be covered by the project results.

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Terminology and acronyms

AHSS	Advanced High Strength Steels
CE	Conformité Européenne (European conformity)
CEN	European Committee for Standardization
CENELEC (CLC)	European Committee for Standardization in the Electrical field
CWA	CEN or CENELEC Workshop Agreement
EC	European Commission
EF	Environmental Footprint methods
EN	European Standard
hEN	Harmonised European standard
ESO	European standardisation organisation
ESPR	Ecodesign for Sustainable Products Regulation
EU	European Union
ISO	International Organization for Standardization; International Standard
NMC	National Mirror Committee
NSB	National Standardization Body
PAS	Publicly Available Specification
SC	Subcommittee
TC	Technical Committee
TR	Technical Report
TS	Technical Specification
UNE	Spanish Association for Standardization
VA	Vienna Agreement
WG	Working Group
WP	Work Package
SME	Small and medium-sized enterprise
OJEU	Official Journal of the European Union
DPP	Digital Product Passport
QR	Quick Response code
NFC	Near Field Communication
LCA	Life Cycle Assessment
PCR	Product Category Rules
PEF	Product Environmental Footprint methods
PEFCR	Product Environmental Footprint Category Rules
OEF	Organisation Environmental Footprint methods
EPD	Environmental Product Declaration

1. Introduction

1.1 Project presentation overview

Steel4Fatigue project is funded by the European Union's Research Funds for Coal and Steel, starting on the 4th of July 2024 with a 42-month duration. The Consortium brings together 9 partners from 4 different countries.

The overall objective of Steel4Fatigue is to investigate fatigue-optimised solutions for dynamic components in the automotive industry, introducing new materials and technologies to reduce the weight of trucks and cars by 10%. These solutions will be based on specially developed materials with high fatigue performance (AHSS and spring steels), advanced computer modelling for accurate fatigue prediction, and innovative experimental methodologies to reduce testing time. The project will also focus on minimising environmental impact evaluated through life cycle assessment, reducing energy consumption and material usage through improved steelmaking processes, and enhancing fatigue performance to facilitate wider market adoption of Steel4Fatigue solutions.

The project's contributions include reducing lead times to market through advanced fatigue testing methodologies and models. The outcomes will provide materials, modelling, and experimental tools for designing fatigue-resistant parts across multiple sectors. Practical guidelines will be established for factors such as proposed microstructures, advanced testing, modelling approaches, and the influence of manufacturing and steelmaking processes on part performance.

The present deliverable contains the analysis of the relevant standardization landscape, consisting of published and under-development standards that can be applicable to Steel4Fatigue project, as well as the standardization Technical Committees (TCs) that could be of use for the project activities.

Attainment of the objectives and explanation of deviations

This deliverable is fully in line with the contractual obligations and the project objectives. There are no deviations in terms of timeline or content.

1.2 Methodology

This document presents the standardisation activity found relevant for the Steel4Fatigue project. In order to structure the research, UNE elaborated a list of key concepts to act as a starting point for the identification of standardisation areas:

- Metallic materials
- Metallic products
- Metallic materials test methods
- Ductility
- Fatigue
- Hardness
- Toughness
- Forming
- Microstructure

- Modelling/Model
- Circular economy
- Life cycle assessment

The identified standardisation areas that structure this document are as follows:

- Steel and steel products
- Steel test methods
- Microstructural characterisation
- Life Cycle

This standardisation study covers European standardisation developed by the European Committee for Standardisation ([CEN](#)) and the International standardisation developed by the International Organization for Standardisation ([ISO](#)).

The study is structured in standardisation areas for which relevant standardisation technical committees (TCs) and other technical bodies within them, published standards, and standards under development (project standards) are referred to. The relationship with the project found for each of the identified areas is explained.

The standards related to steel test methods used in the development of the Steel4Fatigue project have also been included in this study.

1.3 Brief introduction about standardisation

This section provides information about standardisation and standardisation activities related to Steel4Fatigue. The aim is to facilitate basic information to the public not familiar with this concept, to provide the essential vocabulary and knowledge to use this document. The study on existing standardisation technical committees and standards provides information on standardisation activities related to Steel4Fatigue.

1.3.1 Organisation

Standards are voluntary technical documents that set out requirements for a specific item, material, component, system, or service, or describe in detail a particular method, procedure, or best practice. Standards are developed and defined through a process of sharing knowledge and building consensus among technical experts nominated by interested parties and other stakeholders - including businesses, consumers, and environmental groups, among others. These experts are organized in Technical Committees (TCs), which are subdivided into Subcommittees (SCs) or Working Groups (WGs). These TCs are included in the structure of the Standardisation Organizations (National, European, and International, with the respective mirror committees) and work following their internal regulations.

The standardisation bodies operate at national (UNE, UNI, AFNOR, BSI, DIN, ASTM, etc.), regional (CEN, CENELEC, ETSI), or international (ISO, IEC, ITU) level. Sometimes there are different standardisation bodies at the same level but covering different fields. This is the case of ISO (general), IEC (electrical), and ITU (telecommunications) at the international level, or CEN, CENELEC, and ETSI at the European level in the same way.

1.3.2 Documents

There are also diverse kinds of standardisation documents. The most widespread is the standard, which has a different code depending on the organisation under which it was developed, e.g., EN for European Standards, ISO, or IEC for International Standards. Other types of documents are Technical Specifications (TS), Technical Reports (TR), and Workshop Agreements (CWA). Further Amendments to the standards are identified by adding A1, A2, etc., at the end of the standard code.

At the European level, all the members of CEN and CENELEC shall adopt EN standards as national standards and must withdraw any existing national standard that could conflict with them. A summary of the characteristics of the different standardisation documents can be found in Table 1.

Table 1. Characteristics of different standardisation documents

Type	International code	European code	National code	Main characteristics
Standard	ISO IEC	EN	UNE, UNI, NF, BS, DIN, etc. When adopting: UNE-EN, NF-EN, UNE-ISO, NF-ISO, etc.	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Elaboration: 3 years • 2 steps of member approval • European: compulsory national adoption • Revision: every 5 years
Technical Specification	ISO/TS IEC/TS	CEN/TS CLC/TS	When adopting: UNE-CEN/TS, NF-CEN/TS, UNE-ISO/TS, NF-ISO/TS, etc.	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Elaboration: 21 months • 1 step of member approval or internal approval in TC • European: optional national adoption • Revision: at 3 years (upgrading to EN or deletion)
Technical Report	ISO/TR IEC/TR	CEN/TR CLC/TR	When adopting: UNE-CEN/TR, NF-CEN/TR, UNE-ISO/TR, NF-ISO/TR, etc.	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Elaboration: free timeframe • Internal approval in TC • European: optional national adoption • No revision required
Workshop Agreement	IWA	CWA	Variable	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Elaboration: free timeframe (usually few months) • Internal approval in the Workshop • European: optional national adoption • Revision: at 3 years (upgrading to another type of document or deletion)

There is also an agreement established between European and International Organizations (e.g., CEN and ISO) to avoid duplication of efforts and promote global relevance of standards, which allows to adopt or develop in parallel each other's standards with the same content and code. National standards could also be proposed as a base for new European or International standards. Figure 1 shows the tracks of the standards.

Figure 1. Possible tracks of standards adoption

Therefore, the code of any standard is the combination of the above-mentioned issues and could be explained as shown in Figure 2 for a published standard and in Figure 3 for a project standard.

Figure 2. Example of identification of elements in the code of a standard

Figure 3. Example of identification of elements in the code of a standard under development

2. Standardisation areas relevant to steel for fatigue

2.1 Overview of the related standardisation technical committees

The following list, shown in Table 2, presents the European and International committees identified as technical bodies working on subjects related to the Steel4Fatigue project.

It should be noticed that usually there is a correspondence between CEN and ISO standardisation technical committees, and committees with the same scope or a very similar one are found both at the European and at the international level.

It should be noticed too that, despite this double existence of committees, thanks to the agreement established between European and International Organizations, a large number of ISO standards are adopted as CEN standards. This means that two standards with the same reference number may be found in the tables of this clause, as EN and as EN ISO, but it is the same standard with the same technical content. This is the case of "Metallic materials test methods" standards and "Life cycle assessment."

Finally, it is important to highlight three basic rules when talking about European and international standardisation:

- Not all ISO standards are adopted as EN ISO standards.
- EN and ISO standards with the same scope but different technical content can coexist.
- EN and EN ISO standards must be adopted by CEN members as national standards.

Table 2. European and international committees related to the Steel4Fatigue project

Standardisation area	Standardisation Technical Committee
Steel and steel products	CEN/TC 132 Aluminium and aluminium alloys
	CEN/TC 290 Dimensional and geometrical product specification and verification
	CEN/TC 459 ECISS - European Committee for Iron and Steel Standardization
	CEN/TC 459/SC 5 Steels for heat treatment, alloy steels, free-cutting steels and stainless steels
	CEN/TC 459/SC 9 Coated and uncoated flat products to be used for cold forming
	ISO/TC 17 Steel
	ISO/TC 17/SC 3 Steels for structural purposes
	ISO/TC 17/SC 4 Heat treatable and alloy steels
	ISO/TC 17/SC 10 Steel for pressure purposes
	ISO/TC 17/SC 11 Steel castings
	ISO/TC 17/SC 12 Continuous mill flat rolled products
	ISO/TC 213 Dimensional and geometrical product specifications and verification
Steel test methods	CEN/TC 459/SC 1 Test methods for steel (other than chemical analysis)

	CEN/TC 459/SC 2 Methods of chemical analysis for iron and steel
	CEN/TC 459/SC 12 General issues
	CEN/WS FAT4LI Fatigue4Light advanced and fast fatigue testing methods
	CEN/WS FORMPLANET Innovative testing in support of the sheet metal forming industry
	ISO/TC 17/SC 7 Methods of testing (other than mechanical tests and chemical analysis)
	ISO/TC 17/SC 20 General technical delivery conditions, inspection documents and sampling for mechanical testing
	ISO/TC 164 Mechanical testing of metals
	ISO/TC 164/SC 1 Uniaxial testing
	ISO/TC 164/SC 2 Ductility testing
	ISO/TC 164/SC 3 Hardness test
	ISO/TC 164/SC 4 Fatigue, fracture and toughness testing
Microstructural characterization	CEN/TC 352 Nanotechnologies
	ISO/TC 202 Microbeam analysis
	ISO/TC 202/SC 4 Scanning electron microscopy
	ISO/TC 229 Nanotechnologies
Life cycle	CEN/SS S26 Environmental management
	ISO/TC 17/SC 21 Environment related to climate change in the iron and steel industry
	ISO/TC 207 Environmental management
	ISO/TC 207/SC 3 Environmental labelling
	ISO/TC 207/SC 5 Life cycle assessment

2.2 Steel and steel products

This section presents the standardisation technical committees related to steel and steel products and their standards and standards under development, which have been identified as related to the Steel4Fatigue project.

2.2.1 CEN/TC 132 Aluminium and aluminium alloys

Scope

This committee is responsible for the standardisation in the field of unwrought, wrought and cast products made from aluminium and aluminium alloys, particularly: - designations; - terms and definitions; - material specifications; - technical conditions of delivery; - dimensions and tolerances; - methods of testing specific to aluminium.

The technical body sub-structure consists of the following working groups:

- CEN/TC 132/WG 10 Castings
- CEN/TC 132/WG 14 General support
- CEN/TC 132/WG 31 Terminology and general support
- CEN/TC 132/WG 32 Surface treatment and corrosion
- CEN/TC 132/WG 33 Specific applications
- CEN/TC 132/WG 34 Casting and recycling
- CEN/TC 132/WG 35 Extruded products
- CEN/TC 132/WG 36 Rolled products
- CEN/TC 132/WG 5 Extruded and drawn products
- CEN/TC 132/WG 6 Aluminium foil and fin stock
- CEN/TC 132/WG 7 Sheets, strips and plates
- CEN/TC 132/WG 9 Aluminium and aluminium alloys cast and wrought products in contact with food

Further information about scope, published standards, and standards under development can be found through the committee website [CEN/TC 132](#).

2.2.2 CEN/TC 290 Dimensional and geometrical product specification and verification

Scope

This committee is responsible for the standardisation in the field of macro and micro-geometry specification, including dimensional and geometrical tolerancing, surface properties, and the related verification principles, measuring equipment, and calibration requirements.

Further information about scope, published standards, and standards under development can be found through the committee website [CEN/TC 290](#).

Published standards to be considered

The following list, shown in Table 3, presents the published standards to be considered on subjects related to the Steel4Fatigue project.

Table 3. CEN/TC 290 published standards to be considered

Reference	Title
EN ISO 21920-1:2022	Geometrical product specifications (GPS) - Surface texture: Profile - Part 1: Indication of surface texture (ISO 21920-1:2021)
EN ISO 21920-2:2022*	Geometrical product specifications (GPS) - Surface texture: Profile - Part 2: Terms, definitions and surface texture parameters (ISO 21920-2:2021, Corrected version 2022-06)
* Standard used in the Steel4Fatigue project	

2.2.3 CEN/TC 459 ECISS - European Committee for Iron and Steel Standardization

Scope

This committee is responsible for the standardisation of the definition, classification, testing, chemical analysis, and technical delivery requirements for iron and steel products.

The technical body sub-structure consists of the following working groups:

- CEN/TC 459/WG 1 Steel circular economy

Further information about scope, published standards, and standards under development can be found through the committee website [CEN/TC 459](#).

2.2.4 CEN/TC 459/SC 5 Steels for heat treatment, alloy steels, free-cutting steels, and stainless steels

Scope

This committee is responsible for the standardisation of technical delivery conditions for steels for heat treatment and alloy steels, including free-cutting, bright, and tool steels used mainly in the engineering and automotive industry.

The technical body sub-structure consists of the following working groups:

- CEN/TC 459/SC 5/WG 1 Steels for heat treatment, alloy steels and free cutting steels
- CEN/TC 459/SC 5/WG 2 Stainless steels

Further information about scope, published standards and standards under development can be found through the committee website [CEN/TC 459/SC 5](#).

2.2.5 CEN/TC 459/SC 9 Coated and uncoated flat products to be used for cold forming

Scope

This committee is responsible for the standardisation of uncoated and coated steel flat products to be used for cold forming, including, e.g., products for packaging (tin mill products) and products for construction (Requirements, dimensions, tolerances, and specific tests).

The technical body sub-structure consists of the following working groups:

- CEN/TC 459/SC 9/WG 1 Uncoated and coated flat products for cold forming and construction, except tin mill products
- CEN/TC 459/SC 9/WG 2 Tin mill products
- CEN/TC 459/SC 9/WG 3 Hot and cold rolled steels for enamelling
- CEN/TC 459/SC 9/WG 5 Revision of EN 10111 :2008

Further information about scope, published standards, and standards under development can be found through the committee website [CEN/TC 459/SC 9](#).

2.2.6 ISO/TC 17 Steel

Scope

This committee is responsible for the standardisation in the field of cast, wrought, and cold-formed steel, including technical delivery conditions for steel tubes for pressure purposes, environmental issues related to climate change, and emerging technologies in the iron and steel industry.

Excluded:

- steel tubes within the scope of ISO / TC 5.
- line pipe, casing, tubing, and drill pipe within the scope of ISO / TC 67.
- methods of mechanical testing of metals within the scope of ISO / TC 164.

The technical body sub-structure consists of the following subcommittees and working groups:

- ISO/TC 17/SC 1 Methods of determination of chemical composition
- ISO/TC 17/SC 3 Steels for structural purposes
- ISO/TC 17/SC 4 Heat treatable and alloy steels
- ISO/TC 17/SC 7 Methods of testing (other than mechanical tests and chemical analysis)
- ISO/TC 17/SC 9 Tinplate and black plate
- ISO/TC 17/SC 10 Steel for pressure purposes
- ISO/TC 17/SC 11 Steel castings
- ISO/TC 17/SC 12 Continuous mill flat rolled products Subcommittee
- ISO/TC 17/SC 15 Railway rails, rail fasteners, wheels, and wheelsets
- ISO/TC 17/SC 16 Steels for the reinforcement and prestressing of concrete

- ISO/TC 17/SC 17 Steel wire rod and wire products
- ISO/TC 17/SC 19 Technical delivery conditions for steel tubes for pressure purposes
- ISO/TC 17/SC 20 General technical delivery conditions, inspection documents and sampling for mechanical testing
- ISO/TC 17/SC 21 Environment related to climate change in the iron and steel industry
- ISO/TC 17/AG 0 Advisory group
- ISO/TC 17/SG 3 Smart Manufacturing in Iron and Steel Industry (SMISI)
- ISO/TC 17/WG 28 Guideline for smart manufacturing in the iron and steel industry
- ISO/TC 17/WG 29 Revision of ISO 4885
- ISO/TC 17/WG 30 Revision of ISO 4948-1
- ISO/TC 17/WG 31 Establishment of TR on recycled iron-steel raw materials

Further information about scope, published standards, and standards under development can be found through the committee website, [ISO/TC 17](#)

2.2.7 ISO/TC 17/SC 3 Steels for structural purposes

Scope

This committee is responsible for the standardisation of uncoated steels for structural purposes (for bridges, buildings, etc.) and for general engineering purposes (steels not intended for heat treatment by the consumer), in terms of:

- qualities
- dimensions and tolerances for plates, wide flats, bars, and sections, excluding:
 - flat rolled products manufactured on a continuous mill
 - steel for the reinforcement of concrete and prestressing steels
 - wire and wire rods
 - structural hollow sections.

The technical body sub-structure consists of the following working groups:

- ISO/TC 17/SC 3/WG 18 Hot rolled longitudinally profiled steel plate
- ISO/TC 17/SC 3/WG 19 Hot rolled steel sections
- ISO/TC 17/SC 3/WG 20 Hot rolled steel bars

Further information about scope, published standards, and standards under development can be found through the committee website [ISO/TC 17/SC 3](#).

2.2.8 ISO/TC 17/SC 4 Heat treatable and alloy steels

Scope

This committee is responsible for the standardisation of qualities, dimensions, and tolerances of heat-treatable and alloy steels used mainly in the engineering and automotive industry in either the non-heat-treated or the heat-treated conditions. Examples are free-cutting, bright, stainless, heat-resisting, tool, spring, valve, and roller bearing steels, including tubular products for these applications, but not those covered by ISO/TC 5.

The technical body sub-structure consists of the following working groups:

- ISO/TC 17/SC 4/AHG 1 Study on reorganisation of TC 17/SC 4

Further information about scope, published standards, and standards under development can be found through the committee website [ISO/TC 17/SC 4](#).

2.2.9 ISO/TC 17/SC 10 Steel for pressure purposes

Scope

This committee is responsible for the standardisation of:

- Qualities of flat products, bars, and forgings for pressure purposes.
- Methods for deriving and establishing the elevated temperature yield/proof strength and average creep values of steels for pressure purposes.

The technical body sub-structure consists of the following working groups:

- ISO/TC 17/SC 10/WG 1 Revision of ISO 9327-1 to -5 Working group
- ISO/TC 17/SC 10/WG 2 Revision of ISO 9328-1, 2, 4 and 7

Further information about scope, published standards, and standards under development can be found through the committee website [ISO/TC 17/SC 10](#).

2.2.10 ISO/TC 17/SC 11 Steel castings

Scope

This committee is responsible for the standardisation of steel castings and the sampling and conditions of delivery of these for all purposes.

The technical body sub-structure consists of the following working groups:

- ISO/TC 17/SC 11/WG 25 Steel castings

Further information about scope, published standards, and standards under development can be found through the committee website [ISO/TC 17/SC 11](#).

2.2.11 ISO/TC 17/SC 12 Continuous mill flat rolled products

Scope

This committee is responsible for the standardisation of development and maintenance of specifications for hot-rolled and cold-reduced steel sheet and strip in coils and cut lengths, and metallic-coated steel sheet in coils and cut lengths. excluding:

- Tinplate and blackplate, but including tin-coated sheets
- Stainless and heat-resistant steels 3
- Plates.

The technical body sub-structure consists of the following working groups:

- ISO/TC 17/SC 12/AHG 1 Study on double standardization Working group
- ISO/TC 17/SC 12/SG 1 Study on specific products Working group
- ISO/TC 17/SC 12/WG 2 Revision of ISO 20805

Further information about scope, published standards, and standards under development can be found through the committee website [ISO/TC 17/SC 12](#).

2.2.12 ISO/TC 213 Dimensional and geometrical product specifications and verification

Scope

This committee is responsible for the standardisation in the field of geometrical product specifications (GPS), i.e., macro- and microgeometry specifications covering dimensional and geometrical tolerancing, surface properties, and the related verification principles, measuring equipment, and calibration requirements, including the uncertainty

of dimensional and geometrical measurement. The standardization includes the basic layout and explanation of drawing indications (symbols).

Excluded: the definition of the specific proportions and dimensions of drawing indications (symbols) and their execution.

The technical body sub-structure consists of the following working groups:

- ISO/TC 213/AG 1 Strategy and planning
- ISO/TC 213/AG 2 Auditing
- ISO/TC 213/AG 12 Mathematical support group
- ISO/TC 213/AG 13 Identification of user needs
- ISO/TC 213/JSG 1 Joint Advisory Group between ISO/TC 10 and ISOTC 213 for harmonization issues
- ISO/TC 213/WG 2 Datums and datum systems
- ISO/TC 213/WG 4 Uncertainty of measurement and decision rules
- ISO/TC 213/WG 6 General requirements for geometrical product specification (GPS) measuring equipment
- ISO/TC 213/WG 9 Dimensional and geometrical tolerancing for castings
- ISO/TC 213/WG 10 Coordinate measuring machines
- ISO/TC 213/WG 12 Size
- ISO/TC 213/WG 14 Vertical GPS principles
- ISO/TC 213/WG 15 GPS extraction and filtration techniques
- ISO/TC 213/WG 16 Areal and profile surface texture
- ISO/TC 213/WG 17 Facilitation of GPS implementation
- ISO/TC 213/WG 18 Geometrical tolerancing

Further information about scope, published standards, and standards under development can be found through the committee website [ISO/TC 213](https://www.iso.org/committee/213).

Published standards to be considered

The following list, shown in Table 4, presents the published standards to be considered on subjects related to the Steel4Fatigue project.

Table 4. ISO/TC 213 published standards to be considered

Reference	Title
ISO 21920-2:2021*	Metallic materials — Fatigue testing — Axial force-controlled method (will be replaced by ISO/DIS 1099)
* Standard used in the Steel4Fatigue project	

Standards under development to be considered

The following list, shown in Table 5, presents the standards under development to be considered on subjects related to the Steel4Fatigue project.

Table 5. ISO/TC 213 standards under development to be considered

Reference	Title
ISO/DIS 1099*	Metallic materials - Tensile testing - Part 2: Method of test at elevated temperature
* Standard used in the Steel4Fatigue project	

2.3 Steel test methods

This section presents the standardisation technical committees related to steel test methods and their standards and standards under development, which have been identified as related to the Steel4Fatigue project.

2.3.1 CEN/TC 459/SC 1 Test methods for steel (other than chemical analysis)

Scope

This committee is responsible for the standardisation of general methods for mechanical testing, physico-chemical, and nondestructive testing, including, if necessary, the verification and calibration of testing equipment that is used to determine the properties of the steel. If the test standard applies to all metallic materials (in particular cases where the European Standard is based on an International Standard applicable to all metallic materials), the scope can be extended to all metallic materials. NOTE 1: Where product-specific testing is required, test methods must be prepared by the appropriate Technical Committees, unless otherwise decided by CEN/TC 459.

The technical body sub-structure consists of the following working groups:

- CEN/TC 459/SC 1/WG 2 Ultrasonic testing of steel flat products
- CEN/TC 459/SC 1/WG 3 Tensile testing of metallic materials

Further information about scope, published standards, and standards under development can be found through the committee website [CEN/TC 459/SC 1](#).

Published standards to be considered

The following list, shown in Table 6, presents the published standards to be considered on subjects related to the Steel4Fatigue project.

Table 6. CEN/TC 459/SC 1 published standards to be considered

Reference	Title
EN 10160:1999	Ultrasonic testing of steel flat product of thickness equal or greater than 6 mm (reflection method) (will be replaced by prEN 10160 rev)
EN 10307:2001	Non-destructive testing - Ultrasonic testing of austenitic and austenitic-ferritic stainless steels flat products of thickness equal to or greater than 6 mm (reflection method) (will be replaced by prEN 10307 rev)
EN 10371:2021	Metallic materials - Small punch test method
EN ISO 10275:2020	Metallic materials - Sheet and strip - Determination of tensile strain hardening exponent (ISO 10275:2020)
EN ISO 12004-1:2020	Metallic materials - Determination of forming-limit curves for sheet and strip - Part 1: Measurement and application of forming-limit diagrams in the press shop (ISO 12004-1:2020)
EN ISO 12004-2:2021	Metallic materials - Determination of forming-limit curves for sheet and strip - Part 2: Determination of forming-limit curves in the laboratory (ISO 12004-2:2021)
EN ISO 14556:2023	Metallic materials - Charpy V-notch pendulum impact test - Instrumented test method (ISO 14556:2023)
EN ISO 14577-1:2015	Metallic materials - Instrumented indentation test for hardness and materials parameters - Part 1: Test method (ISO 14577-1:2015) (will be replaced by prEN ISO 14577-1)
EN ISO 148-1:2016*	Metallic materials - Charpy pendulum impact test - Part 1: Test method (ISO 148-1:2016) (will be replaced by prEN ISO 148-1 rev)
EN ISO 16808:2022	Metallic materials - Sheet and strip - Determination of biaxial stress-strain curve by means of bulge test with optical measuring systems (ISO 16808:2022)
EN ISO 16859-1:2015	Metallic materials - Leeb hardness test - Part 1: Test method (ISO 16859-1:2015)
EN ISO 20482:2013	Metallic materials - Sheet and strip - Erichsen cupping test (ISO 20482:2013) (will be replaced by prEN ISO 20482 rev)
EN ISO 204:2023	Metallic materials - Uniaxial creep testing in tension - Method of test (ISO 204:2023)
EN ISO 4545-1:2023	Metallic materials - Knoop hardness test - Part 1: Test method (ISO 4545-1:2023)
EN ISO 6506-1:2014	Metallic materials - Brinell hardness test - Part 1: Test method (ISO 6506-1:2014) (will be replaced by prEN ISO 6506-1)
EN ISO 6508-1:2023	Metallic materials - Rockwell hardness test - Part 1: Test method (ISO 6508-1:2023)
EN ISO 6892-1:2019*	Metallic materials - Tensile testing - Part 1: Method of test at room temperature (ISO 6892-1:2019)
EN ISO 6892-2:2018*	Metallic materials - Tensile testing - Part 2: Method of test at elevated temperature (will be replaced by prEN ISO 6892-2)
EN ISO 6892-3:2015*	Metallic materials - Tensile testing - Part 3: Method of test at low temperature (ISO 6892-3:2015)

<u>CEN ISO/TS 6892-5:2025*</u>	Metallic materials - Tensile testing - Part 5: Specification for testing miniaturised test pieces (ISO/TS 6892-5:2025)
<u>EN ISO 7438:2020</u>	Metallic materials - Bend test (ISO 7438:2020)
<u>EN ISO 7799:2000</u>	Metallic materials - Sheet and strip 3 mm thick or less - Reverse bend test (ISO 7799:1985) (will be replaced by prEN ISO 7799 rev)
* Standard used in the Steel4Fatigue project	

Standards under development to be considered

The following list, shown in Table 7, presents the standards under development to be considered on subjects related to the Steel4Fatigue project.

Table 7. CEN/TC 459/SC 1 standards under development to be considered

Reference	Title
<u>prEN 10160 rev</u>	Ultrasonic testing of steel flat product of thickness equal or greater than 6 mm (reflection method)
<u>prEN 10307 rev</u>	Non-destructive testing - Ultrasonic testing of austenitic and austenitic-ferritic stainless steels flat products of thickness equal to or greater than 6 mm (reflection method)
<u>prEN ISO 14577-1</u>	Metallic materials - Instrumented indentation test for hardness and materials parameters - Part 1: Test method (ISO/DIS 14577-1:2024)
<u>prEN ISO 148-1 rev*</u>	Metallic materials — Charpy pendulum impact test — Part 1: Test method
<u>prEN 148-1 rev*</u>	Metallic materials — Charpy pendulum impact test — Part 1: Test method
<u>prEN ISO 20482 rev</u>	Metallic materials — Sheet and strip — Erichsen cupping test
<u>prEN ISO 6506-1</u>	Metallic materials - Brinell hardness test - Part 1: Test method (ISO/DIS 6506-1:2023)
<u>prEN ISO 6892-2*</u>	Metallic materials - Tensile testing - Part 2: Method of test at elevated temperature (will replace EN ISO 6892-2:2018)
<u>prEN ISO 7799 rev</u>	Metallic materials — Sheet and strip 3 mm thick or less — Reverse bend test
(WI=EC101211)	Metallic materials - Tensile testing - Tensile test on foils and strips of metals with a nominal thickness less than 0,200 mm by using computer-controlled testing machines
* Standard used in the Steel4Fatigue project	

2.3.2 CEN/TC 459/SC 2 Methods of chemical analysis for iron and steel

Scope

This committee is responsible for the standardisation methods and equipment for the determination of the chemical composition of iron and steel and related materials to satisfy the requirements of the steel industry:

- to ensure the availability of analytical procedures to support the implementation of European legislation
- to propose and encourage the production and certification of European certified reference materials

The technical body sub-structure consists of the following working groups:

- CEN/TC 459/SC 2/WG 1 Determination of H, C, N, O, and S in steels and ferrous materials
- CEN/TC 459/SC 2/WG 2 Solid samples - Analysis of steels and ferrous materials by XRF and OES techniques
- CEN/TC 459/SC 2/WG 3 Analysis of steels and ferrous materials by ICP and AAS techniques
- CEN/TC 459/SC 2/WG 4 Analysis of steels and ferrous materials by wet chemical methods other than ICP and AAS techniques.
- CEN/TC 459/SC 2/WG 5 Sampling, preparation, evaluation, and quality tools for the analysis of steels and ferrous materials.

Further information about scope, published standards and standards under development can be found through the committee website [CEN/TC 459/SC 2](#).

Published standards to be considered

The following list, shown in Table 8, presents the published standards to be considered on subjects related to the Steel4Fatigue project.

Table 8. CEN/TC 459/SC 2 published standards to be considered

Reference	Title
CEN/TR 10261:2023	Iron and steel - European standards for the determination of chemical composition
CEN/TR 10317:2020	European certified reference materials (EURONORM-CRMs) for the determination of the chemical composition of iron and steel products (will be replaced by prCEN/TR 10317 rev)
* Standard used in the Steel4Fatigue project	

Standards under development to be considered

The following list, shown in Table 9, presents the standards under development to be considered on subjects related to the Steel4Fatigue project.

Table 9. CEN/TC 459/SC 2 standards under development to be considered

Reference	Title
prCEN/TR 10317 rev	European certified reference materials (EURONORM-CRMs) for the determination of the chemical composition of iron and steel products
* Standard used in the Steel4Fatigue project	

2.3.3 CEN/TC 459/SC 12 General issues

Scope

This committee is responsible for the standardisation of designation, general technical delivery conditions, quality control, and documentation for iron and steel products. Standardisation of definitions, classification, and vocabulary for steel and iron products.

Note: These standards are applicable, whenever possible to all metallic materials. These standards provide guidance and specifications for use within other standards.

The technical body sub-structure consists of the following working groups:

- CEN/TC 459/SC 12/WG 4 Requirements for Inspection Documents and Technical Delivery Conditions for Steel Products
- CEN/TC 459/SC 12/WG 5 Revision of EN 10020:2000

Further information about scope, published standards, and standards under development can be found through the committee website [CEN/TC 459/SC 12](#).

Published standards to be considered

The following list, shown in Table 10, presents the published standards to be considered on subjects related to the Steel4Fatigue project.

Table 10. CEN/TC 459/SC 12 published standards to be considered

Reference	Title
EN 10373:2021	Determination of the physical and mechanical properties of steels using models
EN ISO 377:2017	Steel and steel products - Location and preparation of samples and test pieces for mechanical testing (ISO 377:2017)
EN ISO 377:2017/A1:2025	Steel and steel products - Location and preparation of samples and test pieces for mechanical testing - Amendment 1 (ISO 377:2017/Amd 1:2025)
* Standard used in the Steel4Fatigue project	

2.3.4 CEN/WS FAT4LI Fatigue4Light advanced and fast fatigue testing methods

Scope

This workshop (WS) is responsible for the development of two CWAs related to obtaining, in a limited time, the fatigue properties of the materials. The first one, so-called self-heating measurements, is based on the evolution of temperature measurements under cyclic loading. The second one, so-called stiffness method measurements, is based on the evolution of the damage during cyclic loading.

Further information about the scope and published CEN Workshop Agreements (CWA) and under development CWA can be found through the workshop website [CEN/WS FAT4LI](#).

Published standards to be considered

The following list, shown in Table 11, presents the published CWA to be considered on subjects related to the Steel4Fatigue project.

Table 11. CEN/WS FORMPLANET published the CWA to be considered

Reference	Title
CWA 18107-1:2024* (download)	Advanced fatigue testing methods — Part 1: Self-heating measurements
CWA 18107-2:2024 (download)	Advanced fatigue testing methods — Part 2: Stiffness method
* Document used in the Steel4Fatigue project	

CWA 18107-1:2024 and CWA 18107-2:2024 are based on the results of the Fatigue4Light research project, which received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under grant agreement N° 952908. Moreover, this CWA has been developed under the leadership of EURECAT.

2.3.5 CEN/WS FORMPLANET Innovative testing in support of the sheet metal forming industry

Scope

This workshop (WS) is responsible for the development of novel testing methodologies that allow to characterise of metal sheet properties and predict part performance.

Further information about the scope and published CEN Workshop Agreements (CWA) and under development CWA can be found through the workshop website [CEN/WS FORMPLANET](#).

Published standards to be considered

The following list, shown in Table 12, presents the published CWA to be considered on subjects related to the Steel4Fatigue project.

Table 12. CEN/WS FORMPLANET published CWA to be considered

Reference	Title
CWA 17793:2021* (download)	Test method for determination of the essential work of fracture of thin ductile metallic sheets
* Standard used in the Steel4Fatigue project	

CWA 17793:2021 is based on the results of the FormPlanet research project, which received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under grant agreement N° 814517. Moreover, this CWA has been developed under the leadership of EURECAT.

2.3.6 ISO/TC 17/SC 7 Methods of testing (other than mechanical tests and chemical analysis)

Scope

This committee is responsible for the standardisation of methods of testing steel other than:

- mechanical tests
- chemical analysis
- non-destructive tests covered by other ISO/TC 17/SCs and ISO/TC 135.

The technical body sub-structure consists of the following working groups:

- ISO/TC 17/SC 7/WG 9 Methods for evaluating material compatibility in high-pressure hydrogen - Stainless steel pipes
- ISO/TC 17/SC 7/WG 8 Determination of the thickness of surface-hardened layers
- ISO/TC 17/SC 7/WG 7 Metallographic characterization of duplex grain size and distributions
- ISO/TC 17/SC 7/WG 6 The determination of alpha ferrite
- ISO/TC 17/SC 7/WG 5 Evaluation of Centerline Segregation of Continuously Cast Slabs
- ISO/TC 17/SC 7/WG 4 Determination of content of non-metallic inclusions — Micrographic method using standard diagrams

Further information about scope, published standards, and standards under development can be found through the committee website [ISO/TC 17/SC 7](#).

Published standards to be considered

The following list, shown in Table 13, presents the published standards to be considered on subjects related to the Steel4Fatigue project.

Table 13. ISO/TC 17/SC 7 published standards to be considered

Reference	Title
ISO 3763:1976	Wrought steels — Macroscopic methods for assessing the content of non-metallic inclusions
ISO 4967:2013*	Steel — Determination of content of non-metallic inclusions — Micrographic method using standard diagrams (will be replaced by ISO/DIS 4967)
ISO 17577:2016	Steel — Ultrasonic testing of steel flat products of thickness equal to or greater than 6 mm
* Standard used in the Steel4Fatigue project	

Standards under development to be considered

The following list, shown in Table 14, presents the standards under development to be considered on subjects related to the Steel4Fatigue project.

Table 14. ISO/TC 17/SC 7 standards under development to be considered

Reference	Title
ISO/DIS 4967 *	Steel — Determination of the non-metallic inclusion content — Micrographic method (will replace ISO 4967:2013)
* Standard used in the Steel4Fatigue project	

2.3.7 ISO/TC 17/SC 20 General technical delivery conditions, inspection documents, and sampling for mechanical testing

Scope

This committee is responsible for the standardisation of general technical delivery conditions, inspection documents, and general rules for the selection and preparation of samples and test pieces for mechanical testing of wrought steels.

Further information about scope, published standards, and standards under development can be found through the committee website [ISO/TC 17/SC 20](#)

Published standards to be considered

The following list, shown in Table 15, presents the published standards to be considered on subjects related to the Steel4Fatigue project.

Table 15. ISO/TC 17/SC 20 published standards to be considered

Reference	Title
ISO 377:2017	Steel and steel products — Location and preparation of samples and test pieces for mechanical testing
ISO 377:2017/Amd 1:2025	Steel and steel products — Location and preparation of samples and test pieces for mechanical testing — Amendment 1
* Standard used in the Steel4Fatigue project	

2.3.8 ISO/TC 164 Mechanical testing of metals

Scope

This committee is responsible for the standardisation of methods for mechanical testing, including the verification and calibration of equipment that is used to determine the properties of metallic materials.

Excluded: the responsibility for the application of the method and for the results obtained.

Note: This does not preclude product committees from developing tests appropriate to their specific materials.

The technical body sub-structure consists of the following committees:

- ISO/TC 164/CAG Chair's Advisory Group Working group
- ISO/TC 164/SC 2 Ductility testing Subcommittee
- ISO/TC 164/SC 4 Fatigue, fracture and toughness testing Subcommittee
- ISO/TC 164/SC 3 Hardness testing Subcommittee
- ISO/TC 164/WG 2 Measurement uncertainty Working group
- ISO/TC 164/WG 1 Terminology and symbols Working group
- ISO/TC 164/SC 1 Uniaxial testing

Further information about scope, published standards, and standards under development can be found through the committee website [ISO/TC 164](#).

Published standards to be considered

The following list, shown in Table 16, presents the published standards to be considered on subjects related to the Steel4Fatigue project.

Table 16. ISO/TC 164 published standards to be considered

Reference	Title
ISO 23718:2007	Metallic materials — Mechanical testing — Vocabulary (will be replaced by ISO/CD TS 23718)
* Standard used in the Steel4Fatigue project	

Standards under development to be considered

The following list, shown in Table 17, presents the standards under development to be considered on subjects related to the Steel4Fatigue project.

Table 17. ISO/TC 164 standards under development to be considered

Reference	Title
ISO/CD TS 23718	Metallic materials — Mechanical testing — Vocabulary
* Standard used in the Steel4Fatigue project	

2.3.9 ISO/TC 164/SC 1 Uniaxial testing

Scope

This committee is responsible for the standardisation of methods for the determination of properties and characteristics of metallic materials in uniaxial non-cyclical tension or compression, including the calibration and verification of measuring systems

The technical body sub-structure consists of the following working groups:

- ISO/TC 164/SC 1/SG 1 Continuous force calibration
- ISO/TC 164/SC 1/WG 2 Creep and stress relaxation testing
- ISO/TC 164/SC 1/WG 4 Conventional quasi-static tensile test procedures
- ISO/TC 164/SC 1/WG 7 Tensile testing at high strain rates
- ISO/TC 164/SC 1/WG 9 Tensile testing, method in high-pressure hydrogen environment

Further information about scope, published standards, and standards under development can be found through the committee website [ISO/TC 164/SC 1](#).

Published standards to be considered

The following list, shown in Table 18, presents the published standards to be considered on subjects related to the Steel4Fatigue project.

Table 18. ISO/TC 164/SC 1 published standards to be considered

Reference	Title
ISO 204:2023	Metallic materials — Uniaxial creep testing in tension — Method of test
ISO 6892-1:2019*	Metallic materials — Tensile testing — Part 1: Method of test at room temperature
ISO 6892-2:2018*	Metallic materials — Tensile testing — Part 2: Method of test at elevated temperature (will be replaced by ISO/DIS 6892-2)
ISO 6892-3:2015*	Metallic materials — Tensile testing — Part 3: Method of test at low temperature
ISO 6892-4:2015*	Metallic materials — Tensile testing — Part 4: Method of test in liquid helium
ISO/TS 6892-5:2025*	Metallic materials — Tensile testing — Part 5: Specification for testing miniaturised test pieces
* Standard used in the Steel4Fatigue project	

Standards under development to be considered

The following list, shown in Table 19, presents the standards under development to be considered on subjects related to the Steel4Fatigue project.

Table 19. ISO/TC 164/SC 1 standards under development to be considered

Reference	Title
ISO/DIS 6892-2*	Metallic materials - Tensile testing - Part 2: Method of test at elevated temperature (ISO/DIS 6892-2:2025)
* Standard used in the Steel4Fatigue project	

2.3.10 ISO/TC 164/SC 2 Ductility testing

Scope

This committee is responsible for the standardisation of methods for the assessment of ductility and formability of metallic materials and products, including the calibration and verification of specialized measuring systems.

Further information about scope, published standards, and standards under development can be found through the committee website [ISO/TC 164/SC 2](#).

Published standards to be considered

The following list, shown in Table 20, presents the published standards to be considered on subjects related to the Steel4Fatigue project.

Table 20 ISO/TC 164/SC 2 published standards to be considered

Reference	Title
ISO 10275:2020	Metallic materials — Sheet and strip — Determination of tensile strain hardening exponent
ISO 7438:2020	Metallic materials — Bend test
ISO 7799:1985	Metallic materials — Sheet and strip 3 mm thick or less — Reverse bend test
ISO 10275:2020	Metallic materials — Sheet and strip — Determination of tensile strain hardening exponent
ISO 11531:2022	Metallic materials — Sheet and strip — Earing test
ISO 12004-1:2020	Metallic materials — Determination of forming-limit curves for sheet and strip — Part 1: Measurement and application of forming-limit diagrams in the press shop
ISO 12004-2:2021	Metallic materials — Determination of forming-limit curves for sheet and strip — Part 2: Determination of forming-limit curves in the laboratory
ISO 16808:2022	Metallic materials — Sheet and strip — Determination of biaxial stress-strain curve by means of bulge test with optical measuring systems
ISO 16842:2021	Metallic materials — Sheet and strip — Biaxial tensile testing method using a cruciform test piece
* Standard used in the Steel4Fatigue project	

Standards under development to be considered

The following list, shown in Table 21, presents the standards under development to be considered on subjects related to the Steel4Fatigue project.

Table 21. ISO/TC 164/SC2 standards under development to be considered

Reference	Title
ISO/CD 7799	Metallic materials — Sheet and strip 3 mm thick or less — Reverse bend test
ISO/DIS 16630	Metallic materials — Sheet and strip — Hole expanding test
ISO/CD 20482	Metallic materials — Sheet and strip — Erichsen cupping test
ISO/AWI 24270.2	Metallic materials — Sheet and strip — Secondary work embrittlement test method
ISO/AWI 25586	Metallic materials — Sheet and strip — Biaxial bulge test method for sheet metals
* Standard used in the Steel4Fatigue project	

2.3.11 ISO/TC 164/SC 3 Hardness test

Scope

This committee is responsible for the standardisation in the field of indentation testing, specifying different indentation test methods, primarily for metals testing, at length scales ranging from nano to macro. Methods include the measurement of Brinell, Knoop, Leeb, Rockwell, and Vickers hardness, and also Instrumented Indentation Testing (at ambient and elevated temperatures) for hardness and materials parameters, including indentation elastic modulus (both quasi-static and dynamic), indentation creep, elastic and plastic work of indentation, and relative average surface stress. Also included are methods for the verification and calibration of indentation testing and calibration machines, the calibration of reference blocks, the calculation of measurement uncertainties, and the conversion of hardness values.

The technical body sub-structure consists of the following working groups:

- ISO/TC 164/SC 3/AG 1 Uncertainties
- ISO/TC 164/SC 3/SG 1 Expansion of scope for the revision of ISO 16859-1 to -3 - Instrument designs and impact bodies.
- ISO/TC 164/SC 3/WG 2 Revision of the standard series ISO 6506 - Metallic materials - Brinell hardness test
- ISO/TC 164/SC 3/WG 4 Revision of ISO 14577 - Metallic materials - Instrumented indentation test for hardness and materials parameters
- ISO/TC 164/SC 3/WG 5 Vickers hardness test - Knoop hardness test

Further information about scope, published standards, and standards under development can be found through the committee website [ISO/TC 164/SC 3](#).

Published standards to be considered

The following list, shown in Table 22, presents the published standards to be considered on subjects related to the Steel4Fatigue project.

Table 22. ISO/TC 164/SC 3 published standards to be considered

Reference	Title
ISO 4545-1:2023	Metallic materials — Knoop hardness test — Part 1: Test method
ISO 6506-1:2014	Metallic materials — Brinell hardness test — Part 1: Test method
ISO 6507-1:2023	Metallic materials — Vickers hardness test — Part 1: Test method
ISO 6508-1:2023	Metallic materials — Rockwell hardness test — Part 1: Test method
ISO 14577-1:2015	Metallic materials — Instrumented indentation test for hardness and materials parameters — Part 1: Test method (be replaced by ISO/DIS 14577-1)
ISO 14577-4:2016	Metallic materials — Instrumented indentation test for hardness and materials parameters — Part 4: Test method for metallic and non-metallic coatings
ISO 14577-5:2022	Metallic materials — Instrumented indentation test for hardness and materials parameters — Part 5: Linear elastic dynamic instrumented indentation testing (DIIT)
ISO/TR 29381:2008	Metallic materials — Measurement of mechanical properties by an instrumented indentation test — Indentation tensile properties
* Standard used in the Steel4Fatigue project	

Standards under development to be considered

The following list, shown in Table 23, presents the standards under development to be considered on subjects related to the Steel4Fatigue project.

Table 23. ISO/TC 164/SC 3 standards under development to be considered

Reference	Title
ISO/DIS 14577-1	Metallic materials — Instrumented indentation test for hardness and materials parameters — Part 1: Test method
ISO/FDIS 14577-6	Metallic materials — Instrumented indentation test for hardness and materials parameters — Part 6: Instrumented indentation test at elevated temperature
ISO 16859-1:2015	Metallic materials — Leeb hardness test — Part 1: Test method
* Standard used in the Steel4Fatigue project	

2.3.12 ISO/TC 164/SC 4 Fatigue, fracture, and toughness testing

Scope

This committee is responsible for the standardisation of testing methodologies for fatigue, fracture, fracture toughness, and pendulum-impact properties of metallic materials.

Excluded: The responsibility for the application of the methods and for the results obtained.

Note: This does not preclude product committees from developing tests appropriate to their specific materials

The technical body sub-structure consists of the following working groups:

- ISO/TC 164/SC 4/WG 2 Pendulum impact toughness
- ISO/TC 164/SC 4/WG 3 Fracture toughness
- ISO/TC 164/SC 4/WG 4 Advanced apparatus and analysis
- ISO/TC 164/SC 4/WG 5 Fatigue testing: general conditions
- ISO/TC 164/SC 4/WG 6 Fatigue testing: elasto-plastic strain and crack growth conditions

Further information about scope, published standards, and standards under development can be found through the committee website [ISO/TC 164/SC 4](#).

Published standards to be considered

The following list, shown in Table 24, presents the published standards to be considered on subjects related to the Steel4Fatigue project.

Table 24. ISO/TC 164/SC 4 published standards to be considered

Reference	Title
<u>ISO 148-1:2016*</u>	Metallic materials — Charpy pendulum impact test — Part 1: Test method (will be replaced by ISO/CD 148-1)
<u>ISO 1099:2017*</u>	Metallic materials — Fatigue testing — Axial force-controlled method (will be replaced by ISO/DIS 1099)
<u>ISO 4965-1:2012</u>	Metallic materials — Dynamic force calibration for uniaxial fatigue testing — Part 1: Testing systems
<u>ISO 12106:2017</u>	Metallic materials — Fatigue testing — Axial-strain-controlled method (will be replaced by ISO/CD 12106)
<u>ISO 12108:2018</u>	Metallic materials — Fatigue testing — Fatigue crack growth method (will be replaced by ISO/CD 12108)
<u>ISO 12110-1:2013</u>	Metallic materials — Fatigue testing — Variable amplitude fatigue testing — Part 1: General principles, test method and reporting requirements
<u>ISO 12110-2:2013</u>	Metallic materials — Fatigue testing — Variable amplitude fatigue testing — Part 2: Cycle counting and related data reduction methods
<u>ISO 12111:2011</u>	Metallic materials — Fatigue testing — Strain-controlled thermomechanical fatigue testing method (will) be replaced by ISO/CD
<u>ISO 12135:2021</u>	Metallic materials — Unified method of test for the determination of quasistatic fracture toughness
<u>ISO 14556:2023</u>	Metallic materials — Charpy V-notch pendulum impact test — Instrumented test method
<u>ISO 15653:2018</u>	Metallic materials — Method of test for the determination of quasistatic fracture toughness of welds (will be replaced by ISO/CD 15653)
<u>ISO/TS 21913:2022</u>	Temperature verification method applied to dynamic fatigue testing
<u>ISO 22407:2021</u>	Metallic materials — Fatigue testing — Axial plane bending method
<u>ISO 23296:2022</u>	Metallic materials – Fatigue testing – Force controlled thermo-mechanical fatigue testing method (will be replaced by ISO/DIS 23296)
<u>ISO 26843:2015</u>	Metallic materials — Measurement of fracture toughness at impact loading rates using precracked Charpy-type test pieces
<u>ISO 27306:2016</u>	Metallic materials — Method of constraint loss correction of CTOD fracture toughness for fracture assessment of steel components (will be replaced by ISO/CD 26843)
* Standard used in the Steel4Fatigue project	

Standards under development to be considered

The following list, shown in Table 25, presents the standards under development to be considered on subjects related to the Steel4Fatigue project.

Table 25. ISO/TC 164/SC 4 standards under development to be considered

Reference	Title
ISO/CD 148-1*	Metallic materials — Charpy pendulum impact test — Part 1: Test method
ISO/DIS 1099*	Metallic materials — Fatigue testing — Axial force-controlled method
ISO/CD TR 12105	Metallic materials — Fatigue testing — General principles
ISO/CD 12106	Metallic materials — Fatigue testing — Axial-strain-controlled method
ISO/CD 12108	Metallic materials — Fatigue testing — Fatigue crack growth method
ISO/CD 12111	Metallic materials — Fatigue testing — Strain-controlled thermomechanical fatigue testing method
ISO/CD TR 15262	Mechanical tests on metallic materials — Uncertainty in low-cycle fatigue
ISO/CD 15653	Metallic materials — Method of test for the determination of quasistatic fracture toughness of welds
ISO/DIS 23296	Metallic materials – Fatigue testing – Force controlled thermo-mechanical fatigue testing method
ISO/CD 26843	Metallic materials — Measurement of fracture toughness at impact loading rates using precracked Charpy-type test pieces
* Standard used in the Steel4Fatigue project	

2.4 Microstructural characterization

This section presents the standardisation technical committees related to the analysis of methods for microstructural characterization of particles and their standards and standards under development, which have been identified as related to the Steel4Fatigue project.

2.4.1 CEN/TC 352 Nanotechnologies

Scope

This committee is responsible for the standardisation in the field of nanotechnologies, which includes either or both of the following:

- i) understanding and control of matter and processes at the nanoscale, typically, but not exclusively, below 100 nanometres in one or more dimensions, where the onset of size-dependent phenomena usually enables novel applications.

ii) utilizing the properties of nanoscale materials that differ from the properties of individual atoms, molecules, or bulk matter, to create improved materials, devices, and systems that exploit these new properties.

Specific tasks include developing standards for: classification, terminology and nomenclature; metrology and instrumentation, including specifications for reference materials; test methodologies; modelling and simulation; science-based health, safety and environmental practices; and nanotechnology products and processes. Standards in each of these areas could be specific to a product, process, or industry.

The technical body sub-structure consists of the following working groups:

- CEN/TC 352/WG 1 Measurement, characterization and performance evaluation
- CEN/TC 352/WG 3 Health, safety and environmental aspects
- CEN/TC 352/WG 4 Manufactured nano-objects in food additives

Further information about scope, published standards, and standards under development can be found through the committee website [CEN/TC 352](#).

Published standards to be considered

The following list, shown in Table 26, presents the published standards to be considered on subjects related to the Steel4Fatigue project.

Table 26. CEN/TC 352 standards under development to be considered

Reference	Title
EN ISO 19749:2023	Nanotechnologies - Measurements of particle size and shape distributions by scanning electron microscopy (ISO 19749:2021)
* Standard used in the Steel4Fatigue project	

2.4.2 ISO/TC 202 Microbeam analysis

Scope

This committee is responsible for the standardisation in the field of microbeam analysis (measurement, parameters, methods, and reference materials), which uses electrons as an incident beam and electrons or photons as the detection signal. The use of ions for sample preparation and analysis in an electron microscope is also included, with the exception of techniques that use mass-filtered ions as the detected species.

Excluded: Surface analysis techniques which come under the remit of ISO/TC 201.

Note: The purpose is to analyse the compositional and structural characteristics of solid materials. The volume of analysis will generally involve a depth of up to 10 micrometers and a surface area of less than 100 square micrometers.

The technical body sub-structure consists of the following working groups:

- ISO/TC 202/SC 1 Terminology
- ISO/TC 202/SC 2 Electron probe microanalysis
- ISO/TC 202/SC 3 Analytical electron microscopy
- ISO/TC 202/SC 4 Scanning electron microscopy
- ISO/TC 202/AG Future Directions in Microbeam Analysis
- ISO/TC 202/WG 7 Microbeam analysis - Electron Backscatter Diffraction - Measurement of average grain

Further information about scope, published standards, and standards under development can be found through the committee website [ISO/TC 202](https://www.iso.org/committee/202).

Published standards to be considered

The following list, shown in Table 27, presents the published standards to be considered on subjects related to the Steel4Fatigue project.

Table 27. ISO/TC 202 published standards to be considered

Reference	Title
ISO 13067:2020	Microbeam analysis — Electron backscatter diffraction — Measurement of average grain size (will be replaced by ISO/AWI 13067)
ISO 23703:2022	Microbeam analysis — Guidelines for misorientation analysis to assess mechanical damage of austenitic stainless steel by electron backscatter diffraction (EBSD)
ISO 23749:2022	Microbeam analysis — Electron backscatter diffraction — Quantitative determination of austenite in steel
ISO 24173:2024	Microbeam analysis — Guidelines for orientation measurement using electron backscatter diffraction
* Standard used in the Steel4Fatigue project	

Standards under development to be considered

The following list, shown in Table 28, presents the standards under development to be considered on subjects related to the Steel4Fatigue project.

Table 28. ISO/TC 202 standards under development to be considered

Reference	Title
ISO/AWI 13067	Microbeam analysis — Electron backscatter diffraction — Measurement of average grain size
* Standard used in the Steel4Fatigue project	

2.4.3 ISO/TC 202/SC 4 Scanning electron microscopy

Scope

Further information about scope, published standards, and standards under development can be found through the committee website [ISO/TC 202/SC 4](#).

Published standards to be considered

The following list, shown in Table 29, presents the published standards to be considered on subjects related to the Steel4Fatigue project.

Table 29. ISO/TC 202/SC 4 published standards to be considered

Reference	Title
ISO 16700:2016	Microbeam analysis — Scanning electron microscopy — Guidelines for calibrating image magnification
ISO/TS 21383:2021	Microbeam analysis — Scanning electron microscopy — Qualification of the scanning electron microscope for quantitative measurements
ISO 21466:2019	Microbeam analysis — Scanning electron microscopy — Method for evaluating critical dimensions by CD-SEM
ISO/TS 24597:2011	Microbeam analysis — Scanning electron microscopy — Methods of evaluating image sharpness
* Standard used in the Steel4Fatigue project	

2.4.4 ISO/TC 229 Nanotechnologies

Scope

This committee is responsible for the standardisation in the field of nanotechnologies, which includes either or both of the following:

1. Understanding and control of matter and processes at the nanoscale, typically, but not exclusively, below 100 nanometres in one or more dimensions, where the onset of size-dependent phenomena usually enables novel applications,
2. Utilizing the properties of nanoscale materials that differ from the properties of individual atoms, molecules, and bulk matter, to create improved materials, devices, and systems that exploit these new properties.

Specific tasks include developing standards for: terminology and nomenclature; metrology and instrumentation, including specifications for reference materials; test methodologies; modelling and simulations; and science-based health, safety, and environmental practices.

The technical body sub-structure consists of the following working groups:

- ISO/TC 229/CAG Chair's Advisory Group
- ISO/TC 229/JWG 1 Terminology and nomenclature
- ISO/TC 229/JWG 2 Measurement and characterization
- ISO/TC 229/TG 2 Sustainability, consumer and societal dimensions of nanotechnologies
- ISO/TC 229/WG 3 Health, Safety and Environmental Aspects of Nanotechnologies
- ISO/TC 229/WG 4 Material specifications
- ISO/TC 229/WG 5 Products and Applications

Further information about scope, published standards, and standards under development can be found through the committee website [ISO/TC 229](#).

Published standards to be considered

The following list, shown in Table 30, presents the published standards to be considered on subjects related to the Steel4Fatigue project.

Table 30. ISO/TC 229 published standards to be considered

Reference	Title
ISO 19749:2021	Nanotechnologies — Measurements of particle size and shape distributions by scanning electron microscopy
* Standard used in the Steel4Fatigue project	

2.5 Life cycle assessment

This section presents the standardisation technical committees related to life cycle analysis and their standards and standards under development, which have been identified as related to the Steel4Fatigue project.

2.5.1 CEN/SS S26 Environmental management

Scope

Further information about scope, published standards, and standards under development can be found through the committee website [CEN/SS S26](#)

Published standards to be considered

The following list, shown in Table 31, presents the published standards to be considered on subjects related to the Steel4Fatigue project.

Table 31. CEN/SS S26 published standards to be considered

Reference	Title
CEN ISO/TS 14027:2018	Environmental labels and declarations - Development of product category rules (ISO/TS 14027:2017)
EN ISO 14021:2016	Environmental labels and declarations - Self-declared environmental claims (Type II environmental labelling) (ISO 14021:2016) (will be replaced by prEN ISO 14021)
EN ISO 14021:2016/A1:2021	Environmental labels and declarations - Self-declared environmental claims (Type II environmental labelling) - Amendment 1: Carbon footprint, carbon neutral (ISO 14021:2016/Amd 1:2021) (will be replaced by prEN ISO 14021)
EN ISO 14024:2018	Environmental labels and declarations - Type I environmental labelling - Principles and procedures (ISO 14024:2018) (will be replaced by prEN ISO 14024)
EN ISO 14025:2010	Environmental labels and declarations - Type III environmental declarations - Principles and procedures (ISO 14025:2006) (will be replaced by prEN ISO 14025)
EN ISO 14026:2018	Environmental labels and declarations - Principles, requirements and guidelines for communication of footprint information (ISO 14026:2017)
EN ISO 14040:2006/A1:2020*	Environmental management - Life cycle assessment - Principles and framework - Amendment 1 (ISO 14040:2006/Amd 1:2020)
EN ISO 14044:2006	Environmental management - Life cycle assessment - Requirements and guidelines (ISO 14044:2006)
EN ISO 14044:2006/A1:2018	Environmental management - Life cycle assessment - Requirements and guidelines - Amendment 1 (ISO 14044:2006/Amd 1:2017)
EN ISO 14044:2006/A2:2020*	Environmental management - Life cycle assessment - Requirements and guidelines - Amendment 2 (ISO 14044:2006/Amd 2:2020)
EN ISO 14045:2012	Environmental management - Eco-efficiency assessment of product systems - Principles, requirements and guidelines (ISO 14045:2012)
EN ISO 14046:2016	Environmental management - Water footprint - Principles, requirements and guidelines (ISO 14046:2014)
* Standard used in the Steel4Fatigue project	

Standards under development to be considered

The following list, shown in Table 32, presents the under-development standards to be considered on subjects related to the Steel4Fatigue project.

Table 32. CEN/SS S26 standards under development to be considered

Reference	Title
prEN ISO 14024	Environmental statements and programmes for products - Ecolabels (ISO/DIS 14024:2025)
prEN ISO 14025	Environmental statements and programmes for products - Environmental product declarations (EPDs) (ISO/DIS 14025:2025)
prEN ISO 14050 rev	Environmental management — Vocabulary
* Standard used in the Steel4Fatigue project	

2.5.2 ISO/TC 17/SC 21 Environment related to climate change in the iron and steel industry

Scope

This committee is responsible for the standardisation in the field of environmental issues related to climate change, such as low-carbon processes in the iron and steel industry.

The technical body sub-structure consists of the following committees:

- ISO/TC 17/SC 21/AHG 1 Study of ISO 14404 series
- ISO/TC 17/SC 21/WG 1 Revision of ISO 14404-3
- ISO/TC 17/SC 21/WG 2 Guidelines for application of low-carbon technologies in steel plants
- ISO/TC 17/SC 21/WG 3 Life cycle inventory

Further information about scope, published standards, and standards under development can be found through the committee website [ISO/TC 17/SC 21](#).

Published standards to be considered

The following list, shown in Table 32, presents the published standards to be considered on subjects related to the Steel4Fatigue project.

Table 33. ISO/TC 17/SC 21 published standards to be considered

Reference	Title
ISO 14404-1:2024	Calculation method of carbon dioxide emission intensity from iron and steel production — Part 1: Steel plant with blast furnace
ISO 14404-2:2024	Calculation method of carbon dioxide emission intensity from iron and steel production — Part 2: Steel plant with electric arc furnace (EAF)
ISO 14404-3:2024	Calculation method of carbon dioxide emission intensity from iron and steel production — Part 3: Steel plant with electric arc furnace (EAF) and coal-based or gas-based direct reduction iron (DRI) facility
ISO 14404-4:2020	Calculation method of carbon dioxide emission intensity from iron and steel production — Part 4: Guidance for using the ISO 14404 series
ISO 20915:2018	Life cycle inventory calculation methodology for steel products (will be replaced by ISO/DIS 20915)
* Standard used in the Steel4Fatigue project	

Standards under development to be considered

The following list, shown in Table 33, presents the standards under development to be considered on subjects related to the Steel4Fatigue project.

Table 34. ISO/TC 17/SC 21 standards under development to be considered

Reference	Title
ISO/DIS 20915	Life cycle inventory calculation methodology for steel products
ISO/DTR 25088	Guidance for the application of low-carbon technologies in steel plants
* Standard used in the Steel4Fatigue project	

2.5.3 ISO/TC 207 Environmental management

Scope

This committee is responsible for the standardisation in the field of environmental management to address environmental and climate impacts, including related social and economic aspects, in support of sustainable development.

Excluded: test methods of pollutants, setting limit values and levels of environmental performance, and standardization of products.

Note 1: TC 207 is focused on environmental management systems, auditing, verification/validation and related investigations, environmental labelling, environmental performance evaluation, life cycle assessment, climate change and its mitigation and

adaptation, ecodesign, material efficiency, environmental economics, and environmental and climate finance.

Note 2: Where appropriate, the ISO/TC 207 works in cooperation with existing committees on subjects that may support environmental management.

The technical body sub-structure consists of the following committees:

- ISO/TC 207/SC 1 Environmental management systems
- ISO/TC 207/SC 2 Environmental auditing and related practices
- ISO/TC 207/SC 3 Environmental labelling
- ISO/TC 207/SC 4 Environmental performance evaluation
- ISO/TC 207/SC 5 Life cycle assessment
- ISO/TC 207/SC 7 Greenhouse gas and climate change management and related activities
- ISO/TC 207/DCCG Developing Countries Coordination Group
- ISO/TC 207/SLG Strategic Leadership Group
- ISO/TC 207/STTF Spanish translation task force
- ISO/TC 207/TCG Terminology Coordination Group
- ISO/TC 207/TF 1 Communications Working group
- ISO/TC 207/TG 1 Sustainable Finance Coordination
- ISO/TC 207/TG 2 Circular economy coordination

Further information about scope, published standards, and standards under development can be found through the committee website [ISO/TC 207](#)

Published standards to be considered

The following list, shown in Table 34, presents the published standards to be considered on subjects related to the Steel4Fatigue project.

Table 35. ISO/TC 207 published standards to be considered

Reference	Title
IEC 62430:2019	Environmentally conscious design (ECD) — Principles, requirements and guidance
* Standard used in the Steel4Fatigue project	

2.5.4 ISO/TC 207/SC 3 Environmental labelling

Scope

This committee is responsible for the standardization in the field of communication on environmental aspects of products (i.e. goods and services), including related social and economic aspects. Such communication includes various types of environmental statements (e.g., self-declared claims, ecolabelling, environmental product declarations, and environmental footprints) and their associated programmes.

The technical body sub-structure consists of the following committees:

- ISO/TC 207/SC 3/TF 1 Communication and promotion strategy Working group
- ISO/TC 207/SC 3/WG 10 Revision of ISO 14021 Working group
- ISO/TC 207/SC 3/WG 11 Revision of ISO 14024 Working group
- ISO/TC 207/SC 3/WG 12 Revision of ISO 14025

Further information about scope, published standards, and standards under development can be found through the committee website [ISO/TC 207/SC 3](#).

Published standards to be considered

The following list, shown in Table 35, presents the published standards to be considered on subjects related to the Steel4Fatigue project.

Table 36. ISO/TC 207/SC 3 published standards to be considered

Reference	Title
ISO 14020:2022	Environmental statements and programmes for products — Principles and general requirements
ISO 14021:2016	Environmental labels and declarations — Self-declared environmental claims (Type II environmental labelling) (Expected to be replaced by ISO/DIS 14021 within the coming months)
ISO 14021:2016/Amd 1:2021	Environmental labels and declarations — Self-declared environmental claims (Type II environmental labelling) — Amendment 1: Carbon footprint, carbon neutral. Expected to be replaced by ISO/DIS 14024 within the coming months.
ISO 14024:2018	Environmental labels and declarations — Type I environmental labelling — Principles and procedures (Expected to be replaced by ISO/DIS 14024 within the coming months)
ISO 14025:2006	Environmental labels and declarations — Type III environmental declarations — Principles and procedures (Expected to be replaced by ISO/DIS 14025 within the coming months)
ISO 14026:2017	Environmental labels and declarations — Principles, requirements and guidelines for communication of footprint information
ISO/TS 14027:2017	Environmental labels and declarations — Development of product category rules
ISO/TS 14029:2022	Environmental statements and programmes for products — Mutual recognition of environmental product declarations (EPDs) and footprint communication programmes
* Standard used in the Steel4Fatigue project	

Standards under development to be considered

The following list, shown in Table 36, presents the standards under development to be considered on subjects related to the Steel4Fatigue project.

Table 37. ISO/TC 207/SC 3 standards under development to be considered

Reference	Title
ISO/DIS 14021	Environmental statements and programmes for products — Self-declared environmental claims
ISO/DIS 14024	Environmental statements and programmes for products — Ecolabels
ISO/DIS 14025	Environmental statements and programmes for products — Environmental product declarations (EPDs)
* Standard used in the Steel4Fatigue project	

2.5.5 ISO/TC 207/SC 5 Life cycle assessment

Scope

This committee is responsible for the standardization in the field of life cycle assessment and related management systems and tools for products* and the product portfolio of organizations, including related environmental, social, and economic aspects, in support of sustainable development. It includes life cycle-based environmental, social, economic, and technical assessments. Such assessments can apply to, e.g., circularity of resources and eco-efficiency. The outcome of the assessment provides input for decision-making to minimise or prevent potential adverse impacts. The term "products" includes both goods and services.

The technical body sub-structure consists of the following committees:

- ISO/TC 207/SC 5/JWG 14 Joint ISO/TC 207/SC 5 - ISO/TC 323 WG: Secondary materials
- ISO/TC 207/SC 5/TG 2 Circular economy coordination
- ISO/TC 207/SC 5/TG 3 Strategic Business Plan
- ISO/TC 207/SC 5/WG 12 Life cycle assessment -- Requirements and guidelines
- ISO/TC 207/SC 5/WG 15 Social life cycle assessments
- ISO/TC 207/SC 5/WG 16 Eco-Technoeconomic Analyses

Further information about scope, published standards, and standards under development can be found through the committee website [ISO/TC 207/SC 5](#).

Published standards to be considered

The following list, shown in Table 38, presents the published standards to be considered on subjects related to the Steel4Fatigue project.

Table 38. ISO/TC 207/SC 5 published standards to be considered

Reference	Title
ISO 14040:2006	Environmental management — Life cycle assessment — Principles and framework
ISO 14040:2006/Amd 1:2020*	Environmental management — Life cycle assessment — Principles and framework — Amendment 1
ISO 14044:2006	Environmental management — Life cycle assessment — Requirements and guidelines
ISO 14044:2006/Amd 1:2017	Environmental management — Life cycle assessment — Requirements and guidelines — Amendment 1
ISO 14044:2006/Amd 2:2020*	Environmental management — Life cycle assessment — Requirements and guidelines — Amendment 2
ISO 14045:2012	Environmental management — Eco-efficiency assessment of product systems — Principles, requirements and guidelines
ISO 14046:2014	Environmental management — Water footprint — Principles, requirements and guidelines
ISO/TR 14047:2012	Environmental management — Life cycle assessment — Illustrative examples on how to apply ISO 14044 to impact assessment situations
ISO/TS 14048:2002	Environmental management — Life cycle assessment — Data documentation format
ISO/TR 14049:2012	Environmental management — Life cycle assessment — Illustrative examples on how to apply ISO 14044 to goal and scope definition and inventory analysis
ISO/TR 14073:2017	Environmental management — Water footprint — Illustrative examples on how to apply ISO 14046
ISO/TS 14074:2022	Environmental management — Life cycle assessment — Principles, requirements and guidelines for normalization, weighting and interpretation
ISO/TS 14076:2025	Environmental management — Environmental techno-economic assessment — Principles, requirements and guidance
ISO 59014:2024	Environmental management and circular economy — Sustainability and traceability of the recovery of secondary materials — Principles, requirements and guidance

* Standard used in the Steel4Fatigue project

2.6 Documents of interest for the Steel4Fatigue project

This section presents European legislation, methods, and practices that could be of interest for the Steel4Fatigue project, particularly regarding the life cycle assessment section of this document (see 2.5). A brief introduction to European legislation and standards is also provided.

2.6.1 Brief introduction about EU legislation and standardization

European Union Regulations and Directives

In Europe, the legislative framework has evolved from being fundamentally oriented at setting product-related requirements to be met when products are placed on the market, to an equal emphasis on enforcement aspects during the whole life-cycle of products. The New Legislative Framework addresses essential or other legal requirements, product standards, standards and rules for the competence of conformity assessment bodies as well as for accreditation, standards for quality management, conformity assessment procedures, CE marking, accreditation policy, and lately market surveillance policy, including the control of products from third countries.

In Europe, a large number of products are affected by Directives and Regulations, in order to establish harmonised conditions and basic requirements. A relevant example for the present project would be the [Ecodesign for Sustainable Products Regulation](#) (ESPR).

To support the implementation of these Directives and regulations, methods, guides, and tools are also developed in the context of the European Commission (EC), for example, the Environmental Footprint methods (EF).

European Commission Standardization Requests

A Standardisation Request (Mandate) is a demand from the European Commission to the European standardisation organisations (ESOs), such as CEN or CENELEC, to draw up and adopt European standards in support of European policies and legislation, such as Directives and Regulations. Draft mandates are drawn up by the EC services through a process of consultation with a wide group of interested parties (social partners, consumers, SMEs, relevant industry associations, etc.). The European standards, even developed under a mandate and for European legislation, usually remain voluntary in their use. However, when European standards are adopted, National Standardisation Bodies (NSBs) should transpose them into identical national standards and withdraw any conflicting national standards.

A database of Standardization Requests may be found in the [eNorm Platform](#). For more information about Standardisation requests, refer to the [European Commission related webpage](#).

Harmonized standards and European documents

Harmonised European standards (hENs) are the harmonised technical specifications developed by CEN or CENELEC following the mandates given by the European Commission. The Harmonised European standards are identified by the inclusion of an Annex ZA. Manufacturers, other economic operators, or conformity assessment bodies can use harmonised standards to demonstrate that products, services, or processes comply with relevant EU legislation. The references of harmonised standards must be published in the Official Journal of the European Union (OJEU).

2.6.2 Ecodesign for Sustainable Product Regulation (ESPR)

The ESPR (Directive 2009/125/EC and Regulation (EU) 2017/1369), entered into force on 18 July 2024 and replaces the [Ecodesign Directive 2009/125/EC](#), aiming to improve

the sustainability of products placed on the EU market by improving circularity, energy performance, recyclability, and durability. It lays the foundation for the subsequent adoption of concrete rules, either for specific products or based on groups of products with similar characteristics.

This regulation sets requirements for several categories of physical goods, known as “ecodesign requirements,” that provide performance and information rules. These requirements include:

- Improving product durability, reusability, upgradability, and reparability
- Enhancing the possibility of product maintenance and refurbishment
- Making products more energy and resource-efficient
- Addressing the presence of substances that inhibit circularity
- Increasing recycled content
- Making products easier to remanufacture and recycle
- Setting rules on carbon and environmental footprints
- Limiting the generation of waste
- Improving the availability of information on product sustainability

The EC adopted the first ESPR and Energy Labelling working plan in April 2025, setting out the products that will be prioritised over the coming years. Iron and steel, and aluminium will be included in this working plan in 2026 ([ESPR and Energy Labelling Working Plan 2025-30](#)).

Besides these “ecodesign requirements”, the ESPR also contains measures to achieve these goals: the Digital Product Passport (DPP), rules to address the destruction of unsold customer products, and Green Public Procurement.

Within these measures, the DPP constitutes an important instrument to achieve the objectives set by the ESPR. This passport will be mandatory for sectors such as textiles, electronics, and batteries, and will soon be extended to construction, packaging, and other materials.

The DPP is a mandatory digital structure defined by the European Union, which gathers verifiable information about a product's origin, composition, environmental impact, use, maintenance, and end-of-life. It is accessible through technologies such as QR, NFC, or digital identifiers. Its objective is to guarantee full traceability to facilitate repair and reuse, and to ensure that products meet the sustainability requirements set out in the Ecodesign for Sustainable Products Regulation (ESPR). The first DPPs will be fully operational and accessible through the EU prioritised products by February 2027.

The information to be included in the DPP will be identified by the EC, in consultation with all relevant stakeholders, and will depend on the specific product in question. This information can include:

- Product's technical performance
- Materials and their origins
- Repair activities
- Recycling capabilities
- Lifecycle environmental impacts

For more detailed information, refer to the following resources:

- [Ecodesign for Sustainable Products Regulation - European Commission](#)
- [Directive 2009/125/EC and Regulation \(EU\) 2017/1369](#)
- [Implementation of the ESPR](#)
- [ESPR and Energy Labelling Working Plan 2025-30](#)

2.6.3 Product Category Rules

Product Category Rules (PCR) are technical documents that outline specific rules for conducting a Life Cycle Assessment (LCA) and developing an Environmental Product Declaration (EPD) for specific product categories. The PCR ensures that EPDs follow the same methodology, allowing consistent criteria and comparable results for a family of products with equivalent functions, and allows their comparison. The ESPR and the DPP will require that environmental information comes from EPDs prepared according to recognized PCR documents.

An LCA prepared for an EPD has to be developed in accordance with PCRs published as a standard or by a recognised programme, for example: [BRE](#), [EPD International](#), [ICQM](#), [AENOR](#), [IBU](#), [EPD Italy](#).

In the construction sector, European standard EN 15804+A2 is a framework in Europe, with sectoral sub-PCR aligned with this standard. ISO 21930 is the international version for construction products. Sectoral sub-PCR aligned with EN 15804+A2 for steel, iron, and aluminium can also be found (see tables 39 and 40) for construction works. These standards are within the scope of CEN/TC 350 Sustainability of construction works. Further information about scope, published standards, and standards under development can be found through the committee website [CEN/TC 350](#).

Table 39. Published standards related to PCR in the construction sector

Reference	Title
EN 15804:2012+A2:2019	Sustainability of construction works - Environmental product declarations - Core rules for the product category of construction products (will be replaced by prEN 15804 rev)
* Standard used in the Steel4Fatigue project	

Table 40. Under development standards related to PCR in the construction sector

Reference	Title
prEN 15804 rev	Sustainability of construction works - Environmental product declarations - Core rules for the product category of construction products
prEN 17662	Execution of steel structures and aluminium structures - Environmental Product Declarations - Product category rules complementary to EN 15804 for Steel, Iron and Aluminium structural products for use in construction works.
* Standard used in the Steel4Fatigue project	

2.6.4 Product Environmental Footprint Category Rules

Product Environmental Footprint (PEF) and Organisation Environmental Footprint (OEF) methods, known as Environmental Footprint methods, are life cycle assessment (LCA) based methods to measure and communicate the potential life cycle environmental impact of products (goods or services) and organisations. Together they form the basis for the EU Environmental Footprint and are laid down in the [Commission Recommendation \(EU\) 2021/2279](#) on the use of the Environmental Footprint methods to measure and communicate the life cycle environmental performance of products and organisations. These methods build on existing international standards, for example, ISO 14040 and ISO 14044. They provide guidelines for modelling, calculating, and reporting life cycle environmental impacts of products and organisations.

The Product Environmental Footprint (PEF) method provides rules to quantify and communicate the environmental impacts of products (goods or services). These rules are specific requirements for modelling material flows, emissions, and waste streams, enabling a thorough understanding and management of environmental impacts.

Product Environmental Footprint Category Rules (PEFCRs) are specific rules that complement the general PEF methods, providing further specification for a specific product category or sector. They are developed by the EC or private initiatives. In the EC, they are drafted, managed, and updated by the Technical Secretariat. The list of PEFCRs developed and under development (or revision) in the EC is available at the following link: [PEF METHOD - Green Forum - European Commission](#). Recognised programmes (private initiatives) for developing PCRs are conducted by a PCR Committee, based on an open, transparent, and participatory process at an international level, European level, and national level, for example: [BRE](#), [EPD International](#), [ICQM](#), [AENOR](#), [IBU](#), and [EPD Italy](#).

3. Conclusions

As a result of the analysis of the standardisation landscape at European (CEN) and International level (ISO) presented in this report, the following conclusions may be drawn:

1. There are several European and International technical committees, as well as standards related to the Steel4Fatigue project that may be helpful for its future dissemination. Two, deliverables developed within CEN/WS FAT4LI: CWA 18107-1:2024 “Advanced fatigue testing methods — Part 1: Self-heating measurements” and CWA 18107-2:2024 Advanced fatigue testing methods — Part 2: Stiffness method”.
2. Specific tasks related to the standardisation works of the identified TCs may be performed. Depending on the assessment by Steel4Fatigue partners of the impact of the identified standardisation TCs on their tasks and the level of contribution that their results can represent for these committees, several actions could be performed, for example:
 - Follow-up of TCs' standardisation activities through updates reported by UNE.
 - Dissemination of the Steel4Fatigue project progress by delivering reports to the Secretaries of the relevant TCs or by attending relevant technical committees' meetings.
 - Identification and proposal of standardisation activities to relevant TCs, e.g., development of standardisation deliverables or revision of published standards.
3. The Technical Committees included in this report have a relationship with the Steel4Fatigue project, but different contributions to standardisation could be made depending on the TC standardisation area. The Steel and steel products related TCs are more adequate for dissemination activities. Furthermore, TCs related to mechanical testing of steel are more adequate for dissemination and standardisation proposal activities. A proposal for possible interactions with the standardisation system is given in Table 41.
4. While all the technical committees included in this report have some relation to the Steel4Fatigue project, the most relevant are those related to testing methods for steel, as they are directly related to the project's objectives. A close relationship with these committees should be established for continuous bidirectional information, and especially in the case that some Steel4Fatigue results are expected to be standardised or included in standardisation deliverables. being these:
 - CEN/TC 459/SC 1 Test methods for steel
 - ISO/TC 164 Mechanical testing of metals
 - ISO/TC 164/SC 4 Fatigue, fracture and toughness testing

Table 41. Proposal for possible interactions with standardisation technical committees

Standardisation area	Standardisation Technical Committee	Interaction activities	
		Dissemination	Dissemination and cooperation
Steel and steel products	CEN/TC 459 ECISS - European Committee for Iron and Steel Standardization	✓	
	CEN/TC 459/SC 5 Steels for heat treatment, alloy steels, free-cutting steels and stainless steels	✓	
	ISO/TC 17 Steel	✓	
	ISO/TC 17/SC 4 Heat treatable and alloy steels	✓	
Steel test methods	CEN/TC 459/SC 1 Test methods for steel (other than chemical analysis)		✓
	ISO/TC 17/SC 7 Methods of testing (other than mechanical tests and chemical analysis)		✓
	ISO/TC 164 Mechanical testing of metals		✓
	ISO/TC 164/SC 4 Fatigue, fracture and toughness testing		✓

4. References

CEN and CENELEC Website (<https://www.cencenelec.eu>)

CEN/CENELEC Projex Online database (projex.cen.eu) (restricted to authorized users)

ISO Website (www.iso.org)

ISO Project Portal (isotc.iso.org) (restricted to authorized users)

European Commission Website (https://commission.europa.eu/index_en)

EURlex – access to European Union law (<https://eur-lex.europa.eu/homepage.html?lang=en>)